

First record of predation by *Hoplias malabaricus* (Characiformes: Erythrinidae) on *Leptodactylus paranaru* (Anura: Leptodactylidae) in the Atlantic Forest of southeastern Brazil

Lucas Aosf ^{1*} & Thiago A. S. Oliveira ²

¹ Instituto de Manejo da Biodiversidade (IMBio),
Rua Manoel Carneiro, 89, sala 1, Vila Jacobelli,
CEP 12.505.250, Guaratinguetá, São Paulo, Brazil.

² Engpacto soluções ambientais

Rua Dr. Antônio Castro Prado, 396, Taquaral,
CEP 13076-130, Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil

* Corresponding author: lucasaosf@gmail.com

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Resumo

Hoplias malabaricus (Bloch, 1794) é um peixe predador neotropical conhecido por sua dieta generalista, que inclui o consumo oportunista de anfíbios. *Leptodactylus paranaru* é um anuro recentemente descrito, com distribuição restrita à Mata Atlântica. Este estudo documenta o primeiro registro de predação de *H. malabaricus* sobre *L. paranaru*, observado em um riacho eutrofizado em Praia Grande, estado de São Paulo. Descrevemos a interação e discutimos como as características ambientais do local podem ter facilitado o registro do evento. Este relato contribui para o conhecimento da história natural de ambas as espécies e reforça o comportamento oportunista de *H. malabaricus*.

Palavras-chave

Comportamento; Dieta; Eutrofização; História Natural; Interação predador-presa; Observação

Abstract

Hoplias malabaricus (Bloch, 1794) is a Neotropical predatory fish known for its generalist diet, which includes the opportunistic consumption of amphibians. *Leptodactylus paranaru* is a recently described anuran with a restricted distribution in the Atlantic Forest. This study documents the first record of predation by *H. malabaricus* on *L. paranaru*, observed in a eutrophic stream in Praia Grande, state of São Paulo. We describe the interaction and discuss how the environmental characteristics of the site may have facilitated the event's record. This report contributes to the knowledge of the natural history of both species and reinforces the opportunistic behavior of *H. malabaricus*.

Keywords

Behavior; Diet; Eutrophication; Natural History; Observation; Predator-Prey Interaction

H*oplias malabaricus* (Bloch, 1794) is a freshwater predatory fish widely distributed across South America (Fowler, 1950; Oyakawa, 2003), known for its ambush-hunting strategy and dietary plasticity. Although adults are predominantly piscivorous (Knöppel, 1970; Carvalho et al., 2002), opportunistic predation on amphibians, including anurans and caecilians, has been reported (Silva et al., 2007; Torres, 2018). In Paraná state, Brazil, *H. malabaricus* was recorded preying upon the aquatic caecilian *Chthonerpeton viviparum* Parker & Wettstein, 1929 (Silva et al., 2007), and in Argentina, an individual was observed attempting to ingest a juvenile rattlesnake, *Crotalus durissus terrificus* (Laurenti, 1768), as reported by Torres (2018). These records highlight the opportunistic behavior of the species and its ecological relevance as a predator of diverse vertebrates in freshwater environments.

Among the potential targets of such predation is *Leptodactylus paranaru*, an anuran recently described by Magalhães et al. (2020). This species is a potential prey, as its distribution and habitat use (Magalhães et al., 2020) is shared with *H. malabaricus* (Fowler, 1950; Oyakawa, 2003). This predator is known to occupy the same lentic environments that *Leptodactylus* species use for reproduction (Andrade et al., 2012), and the increased exposure during calling activity is a known predation risk for anurans (Moura et al., 2022).

On 20 July 2025, at approximately 19:10h, we observed a predation event in a slow-flowing, eutrophic stream running parallel to a road (Fig. 1) in the municipality of Praia Grande, state of São Paulo, Brazil (-24.069°, -46.576°; datum WGS84). In this environment, an individual of *Hoplias malabaricus* was preying on an individual of *Leptodactylus paranaru* (Fig. 2). When we first detected the interaction, the fish was already grasping the posterior region of the anuran and beginning the ingestion. The frog actively resisted, attempting to swim towards the surface, while the fish pulled it downward. The struggle lasted approximately 10 minutes, after which the fish descended into deeper water with the frog still in its mouth, and neither was seen again. We remained at the site for an additional 12 minutes to check whether *L. paranaru* would

resurface, but it did not. We therefore infer that the predation event was successful.

Figure 1. Predation event recorded in Praia Grande, São Paulo, Brazil. (A) Lentic and eutrophic environment parallel to the road where the event was recorded. (B) *Hoplias malabaricus* preying on an individual of *Leptodactylus paranaru*.

The environmental context may have facilitated our detection of the interaction. The observed location was an anthropized urban area, where the linear flow of the stream alongside the road formed a narrow, visible habitat. Direct visual observations of predation on amphibians are known to be rare and largely opportunistic (Rocha-Santos et al., 2022), indicating that most events go unnoticed in complex or extensive habitats. The environment where we witnessed the event fits the type of linear habitats that increase detectability (Langley et al., 2018). This record therefore contributes to the growing documentation of amphibian predation by *H. malabaricus*, particularly in interactions rarely observed in the field.

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REFERENCES

- Andrade E.B., Lima-Júnior T.B., Andrade J.M.A.L., Leite J.R.S.A. 2012. Predation by native fish and feeding by crab species on *Leptodactylus macrosternum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926 (Anura: Leptodactylidae) in northeastern, Brazil. *Herpetology Notes* 5:173–175.
- Bloch M.E. 1794. Naturgeschichte der ausländischen Fische. Vol. 8. J. Morino, Berlin.
- Carvalho L., Velasques Fernandes C.H., Moreira V.S. 2002. Feeding preferences of *Hoplias malabaricus* in the Vermelho River, South Pantanal, Brazil. *Revista Brasileira de Zoociências* 4:227–236.
- Fowler H.W. 1950. Os peixes de água doce do Brasil. *Arquivos de Zoologia do Estado de São Paulo* 6:205–404.
- Knöppel H.A. 1970. Food of central Amazonian fishes. *Amazoniana* 2:257–352.
- Langley J.G., Grim K., Linder D., Wilson E., Green S., Foley D.H. 2018. Roads Facilitate Spatial and Temporal Recording of Herpetofauna. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 13:572–581.
- Laurenti J.N. 1768. Specimen medicum, exhibens synopsis reptilium emendatam cum experimentis circa venena et antidota reptilium austriacorum. Joan. Thomae, Viennae.
- Magalhães F.M., Haddad C.F.B., Garda A.A. 2020. A new cryptic species of *Leptodactylus* (Anura: Leptodactylidae) from the Atlantic Forest of southeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa* 4743:401–435.
- Moura M.R., Santana D.J., Mângia S., Feio R.N. 2022. *Leptodactylus vastus* (Leptodactylidae) predation on an endemic frog, *Rupirana cardosoi* (Hylidae), and a compilation of its diet. *Caldasia* 44:205–209.
- Oyakawa O.T. 2003. Family Erythrinidae (Trahiras). In Reis R.E., Kullander S.O., Ferraris Jr C.J. (Eds.), Checklist of the freshwater fishes of South and Central America. EDIPUCRS. 238–240.
- Parker H.W., Wettstein O. 1929. A new caecilian from S. Brazil. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* 10:594–596.
- Rocha-Santos G.C., Almeida-Santos P., Almeida-Santos M. 2022. Predation on amphibians and reptiles by spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in Brazil. *Herpetology Notes* 15:599–612.
- Silva F.F.G., Mott T., Garey M.V., Vitule J.R.S. 2007. *Chthonerpeton viviparum* in Paraná state, Brazil, and the first record of predation by *Hoplias malabaricus*. *Pan-American Journal of Aquatic Sciences* 2:261–262.
- Torres P.J. 2018. Interaction between *Hoplias malabaricus* and *Crotalus durissus terrificus* in Santa Fe, Argentina: Predation attempt or necrophagy? *Boletín de la Asociación Herpetológica Española* 29:42–43.

Lucas Aosf. is a biologist and researcher affiliated with the Institute for Biodiversity Management (IMBio), focusing on the natural history, ecology, and bioacoustics of wildlife. His field research concentrates on the Paraíba Valley in São Paulo state and the Mantiqueira, Bocaina, and Serra do Mar mountain ranges, where he generates data that supports animal release initiatives in collaboration with the Environmental Military Police. He also works as a consultant on wildlife diagnosis and monitoring projects across multiple Brazilian biomes.

Thiago Oliveira. is a biologist and naturalist enthusiast, dedicated to understanding ecological interactions and developing practices aimed at the conservation of natural ecosystems. He works on projects involving the diagnosis, monitoring, and evaluation of fauna and flora, as well as environmental education initiatives.